

Nymphaea alba nsubsp. ×*borealis* comb. et stat. nov. (Nymphaeaceae)

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Abstract—*Nymphaea* ×*borealis* is demoted to the rank of nothosubspecies under the name *Nymphaea alba* nsubsp. ×*borealis*.

The hybrid *Nymphaea alba* subsp. *alba* × *Nymphaea alba* subsp. *candida* is usually referred to as *Nymphaea* ×*borealis*, but this name is only correct when both parent taxa are recognized at the rank of species.

***Nymphaea alba* nsubsp. ×*borealis* (E.G.Camus) M.van der Meer comb. et stat. nov.**

≡ *Nymphaea* ×*borealis* E.G.Camus [*N. alba* L. × *N. candida* J.Presl & C.Presl]
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Nymphaea alba L. subsp. *alba* ×
Nymphaea alba L. subsp. *candida* (J.Presl & C.Presl) Korsh.

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